

The Role Of Health Promotion And Family Support With Attitude Of Couples Childbearing Age In Following Family Planning Program In Health

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ABSTRACT

Background: Problems that affect the attitude of spouses of fertile age (EFA) program in Family Planning (KB) including the lack of a role for health promotion and support of her husband so that the EFA has not been able to regulate the number and spacing, prevent pregnancy repeatedly in the time period is too short. The purpose of this research is to know Relations Role Of Health Promotion And Support Husband With Attitude Of Couples Childbearing Age.

Methods: This research design was analitik korelasional with cross sectional approach. The respondents was taken with a purposive sampling technique that meets the criteria of inclusion and exclusion. The population studied was all Couples Childbearing Age In Health Center South Territory City Kediri with a sample of 522 people.

Results: The results showed that Health Promotion known that the majority of respondents in the Good categories as many as 300 (58%) respondents. Support Husband known that the majority of respondents in the Enough categories as many as 222 (52%) respondents. Attitude Of Couples Childbearing Age In Following Family Planning Program known that the almost half of respondents in the Enough categories as many as 222 (42%) respondents. Results of data analysis showed that $P = 0,000 < \alpha = 0,05$ so H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted which means there Relations Role Of Health Promotion And Support Husband With Attitude Of Couples Childbearing Age In Following Family Planning Program In Health Center South Territory City Kediri.

Conclusion: Based on the results of the study it can be concluded that the role of health care workers and family support to EFA is optimal but consciousness in the EFA should be able to find out about the benefits of following the birth so that couples of childbearing age can cope with the number and spacing of children in the family.

Keywords : Health Promotion, Family Support, Couples Childbearing Age, Family Planning Program

BACKGROUND

Some problems affecting the attitude of Elderly Couple (PUS) in following Family Planning (KB) programs include lack of health promotion officer role in providing health education about the importance of family planning (KB) that can overcome the number of children

in the family. . In addition to regulating the number and spacing of births, the benefits of preventing pregnancy repeatedly in a period that is too short, so that the mother's health can be maintained (BKKBN, 2015).

The support of non-supportive husbands is caused by a lack of information, lack of education, lack of

knowledge, attitudes and practices and the understanding that family planning is a women's business, in addition to an undeveloped male family planning tool and some women do not want it. Their husbands use contraceptives with a variety of reasons that affect the attitudes and behaviors of couples of childbearing age following the Family Planning (KB) program (Adioetomo & Sarwino, 2010).

The number of family planning acceptors in Indonesia has increased since 1994. In 2007 there were approximately 38.9 million fertile-age couples (PUS), about 69.1% of them were family planning acceptors, and 31.9% participated in family planning. In 2013 KB acceptor in Indonesia was recorded at 76.73% (Ministry of Health, 2014). The number of EFA in East Java in 2010 was 8,416,637 people. Of the number of EFAs who became new participants of KB as many as 832,423 people (9, 89%) and active KB participants as many as 5,828,183 people (69, 25%). Active KB coverage is still below the target of 70% (DinKes Jawa Timur, 2010).

Preliminary data obtained from Puskesmas Kota Selatan Selatan Kediri City there are number of EFA in 2013 as many as 4,798 people who follow KB as many as 2,956 people, while those who do not follow KB as many as 1.823 people (39%), the number of EFA 2014 as many as 4923 people who follow KB 3211 people who do not follow KB as many as 1712 people (35%), and in 2015 the number of PUS as many as 4,363 people who follow KB as 3214 people who do not follow KB as much as 1722 people (35%), In 2016 the number of EFA as many as 400 people, as many as 340 souls while those who did not follow KB as many as 60 people. (Preliminary Data at South Kediri South Health Center, 2015).

Preliminary study results conducted on February 26, 2016 in the Working Area of Puskesmas South Kota Kediri Selatan with interviews with 3 people who participated in KB KB said that they took the initiative to follow the family planning program to limit the number of children because it is considered a lot of children are very troublesome and will also cause economic problems. Interviews were also conducted on 3 EFAs who did not participate in family planning programs, because they still wanted children. Reasons that are quite prominent are the lack of family support, fear of side effects and health problems from the use of contraceptives, in addition there is an answer for 10 years the absence of health workers who do socialization or counseling about family planning. Program so they decided not to use contraception.

Many factors lead to reduced attitudes of infertile couples (PUS) to participate in family planning programs including the role of health promotion officers and husbands support. To cause the attitude of the infertile couple in participating in the family planning program is largely the role of health promotion officers who are the media in the growing understanding of (EFA) in the community. The success and failure of health promotion officers is often identified with the success and failure of health promotion officers in encouraging community participation and participation in family planning programs in the work area, health promotion officers are required to work systematically, harmoniously planned. working mechanisms with community stores, areas of leaders and other relevant partners (Dawn, 2014; Sodik, 2014).

Factors influencing husbands' support for the participation of wives in

family planning programs, these factors include: predisposing factors consisting of knowledge, attitudes, beliefs, values of children and desire to have them, age, education level, number of children, employment, income, socio-cultural to family planning, the second is the enabling factors consisting of development programs, the availability of family planning, access to family planning services, and the third is the supporting factors comprising the role of community leaders and roles. health workers (BKKBN, 2008).

METHODS

Design The research used was correlational analytic with Cross Sectional method approach where the researcher did observation or measurement of independent and dependent variable performed simultaneously and performed once (Siyoto and Sodik, 2015). Population in this research is All Pria Age of Fertile (PUS) Which Have Not Followed Family Planning Program Year 2016 amounted to 60 people and the sample is part of population amounting 52 people In Puskesmas City of South Region of Kediri City. The method in this research is Purposive Sampling. Data management in this study include: Editing, Coding, Scoring, and Tabulating.

RESULTS

Health Promotion At Puskesmas City of Southern Region of Kediri City

Health Promotion at Public Health Center of South City of Kediri City is known that most of respondent in Good category is 30 (58%) responder. This is because health promotion officers promote direct family planning programs with face-

to-face responders where staff provides advice and opportunities for respondents to ask about family planning programs. Based on data from the tabulation of questionnaires it is known that from 11 respondents said health workers always do health promotion about KB so that it can be able to increase knowledge of respondents about KB.

The result of this research is supported by research conducted by Nurfadhila Ahmad (2016) with title of research of Family Planning Counseling With Participation of Elderly Age Couple (PUS) Become Family Planning Acceptors in Polohungo Sub-district, Gorontalo District. Based on the research, 97 respondents (58%) had ever received family planning counseling, with the participation of fertile-age couples as family acceptors of 127 respondents (77%). The result of statistical test found that $p = 0,000$ means that there is a relationship between KB counseling with the participation of fertile-age couples into family planning acceptors in Polohungo urban village.

Based on the result of cross-tabulation between Age with Health Promotion At Puskesmas City of South City of Kediri City it is known that most of respondent with Age 20-30 Year in Good category is counted 24 (57%) responder. This is caused by the age of EFA is increasingly mature so that in making decisions always agreed with their partners without taking their own decisions. This is supported by research conducted by Eka Prasetya Budi Rahayu (2015) where the age of husband is more mature so that in giving information about KB to wife limited to its knowledge as can prevent pregnancy, but beside that knowledge husband always support wife by actively delivering his wife

kepuskesmas to be able to get information about the benefits of family planning.

Based on the result of cross-tabulation between Education and Health Promotion at Health Center of South City of Kediri City, it is known that most respondents with high school education level in Good category is 17 (63%) respondents. This is caused by good respondent's education so that in following health promotion conducted by officer can be understood and understood so that the given material can add insight to thinking of EFA about the benefits of joining family planning program. This is supported by the research conducted by Rochmah (2012) from the correlation test between education with the use of long-term contraceptive tool, it can be concluded that education has a strong relationship to the long-term use of contraception in the working area of Gandus Palembang Community Health Center. education and good knowledge are the main requirements to achieve successful use of family planning. If the family planning acceptors already have sufficient knowledge about family planning then the acceptors will not hesitate in using contraceptives.

Based on cross tabulation result between Work and Health Promotion at Public Health Center of South City of Kediri City it is known that almost all respondents work as Entrepreneur / Entrepreneur / Trafficking in Good category is as much as 22 (76%) respondents. This is because information and knowledge about family planning is derived from experience gained from peers so that the benefits of family planning can be understood by the respondents and thus the respondents can follow the family planning program. This is supported by research conducted by Endah Widoro Rahayu (2014) where one's work can

influence the attitude and behavior of EFA in participating in family planning program. This is supported by the lack of information between the two fertile-age couples in determining or taking a decision so as to influence EFAs not following KB. However, by sharing the good time between work and family especially the importance of following KB will add attention and affection between the two EFAs.

Based on the facts obtained from survey results and questionnaires distributed to respondents in Puskesmas City of Southern Region of Kediri City known that health promotion that has been done has been optimal where many PUS in the region are able to know and follow the program KB. So that the health officer of Puskesmas City of South Region of Kediri City able to conclude that with the awareness of society along the development of time so that people besides knowing directly KB program from health officer, the public also can know by internet / media on line, TV, Radio and as so capable increase community insight about KB.

Support Husband In Puskesmas City Southern Region Kediri City

Support Husband In Puskesmas City Southern Region of Kediri City note that most respondents in the category Enough is as much as 27 (52%) of respondents. This is because the husband always provide information, advice and spirit to the wife to follow the family planning program. Where according to one statement of respondents who say that by following KB will be able to minimize the risk of getting pregnant. Based on data from the tabulation of the questionnaire, it is known that from 11 respondents, it is known that husband support is very

optimal in giving advice, motivation to wife to follow KB. It is characterized by the EFA always conducts the nearest healthcare consultation to get KB syringe services.

Based on cross tabulation result between Age with Support of Husband at Health Center of South City of Kediri City, it is known that almost half of respondents with 20-30 year age in Enough category are 20 (48%) respondents. This is due to the increasingly mature husband's age so that in providing information about family planning to the extent of his knowledge as to prevent pregnancy, but in addition to this knowledge husband always support the wife by actively delivering his wife to the nearest health center to be able to get information about the benefits of family planning.

The results of this study is supported by the results of research conducted by Revelation (2012) where the increasing age of a person then the insight of thinking and knowledge will be better so vice versa immature age of a person then attitude and behavior will pay more attention to themselves than to others in this support which the husband gave to his wife to be able to follow the family planning program (Sodik, 2015)

Based on cross tabulation result between Education with Support of Husband in Puskesmas City of South City of Kediri City it is known that almost half of respondents with high school education level in Enough category are as many as 13 (48%) respondents. This is due to the level of education of a good husband so that every time officers do health promotion about family planning, both EFA always actively follow the activity. The results of this study are supported by research conducted by Bela Novita Amaris

Susanto (2015) where it is known that a good level of education will affect the decision making use of contraceptives so that mothers can receive and understand information about the use of contraceptives in decision making use of contraception.

Based on the tabulated cross-tabulation table between Jobs and Husband Support in Puskesmas City of South City of Kediri City it is known that most respondents work as Entrepreneur / Entrepreneur / Trade in Enough category is as many as 16 (55%) respondents. This is caused by the respondent's spelling as a trader where when the health counseling conducted by the officer then the husband will pick up the wife to be active follow the counseling so that it can add insight EFA about KB.

Based on the facts obtained from survey results and questionnaires distributed to the respondents in Puskesmas Kota South Kediri City is known that support the husband to the wife to follow KB where the husband always provide information, advice and spirit to the wife to follow the family planning program.

Pair Attitudes Age Aged (EFA) In Following Family Planning Program In Puskesmas City Southern Region of Kediri City

The Attitude of Elderly Age Couple (PUS) In Following Family Planning Program at Public Health Center of South City of Kediri City, it is known that almost half of the respondents in the Good category are 22 (42%) respondents. This is because there is no prohibition on religion and custom which prohibits to follow KB so that there are respondents

who want to follow the program because the respondent has never followed KB. The existence of support from the husband so that the wife can follow KB. Based on the results of interviews with one of the respondents found that her husband only accompanied the wife to conduct family planning consultation at the nearest health service and also the attitude of husband who did not want to follow KB because of husband's knowledge that KB is only devoted to women.

Based on the results of cross-tabulation between Age and Attitude of Elderly Age (EFA) In Following Family Planning Program In Puskesmas City of South City of Kediri City it is known that almost half of the respondents with Age 20-30 years in the Enough category are 17 (38%) respondents. This is caused by the age of the more mature respondents so that in determining the attitude to follow KB should be supported with good support from the husband. The more mature one's age then the change in attitude and behavior will change with age. This will be a determinant of decisions to be taken, especially the attitude of couples of childbearing age in following KB activities (Ministry of Health, 2014).

Based on the results of cross-tabulation between Education and Attitude of Elderly Age Couple (PUS) In Following Family Planning Program In Puskesmas City of Southern Region of Kediri City it is known that most respondents with high school education level in category enough is 14 (52%) respondents. This is due to good respondent education so that in the formation of attitudes and behavior in making decisions with their partners should be based on good knowledge about family planning. Thus, the decision taken is not detrimental between the two parties.

Based on the results of cross-tabulation between Work and PUS Attitudes Aged In Following Family Planning Program In Puskesmas City of Southern City of Kediri City it is known that almost half of the respondents work as Entrepreneur / Entrepreneur / Trafficking in Good category is as much as 13 (45%) respondents. This is due to the busy work every day but the fertile age couples do not forget the schedule to get KB immunization every time posyandu.

Analyzing Relationship Role of Health Promotion And Husband Support With Pope Attitudes Aged Fertile (PUS) In Following Family Planning Program In Puskesmas City Southern Region Kediri City

The result of data analysis shows that the value of $P = 0,005 < \alpha = 0,05$ thus There is Relation Role of Health Promotion And Support Of Husband With Patient Age Generation Attitude (PUS) In Following Family Planning Program In Puskesmas City South of Kediri City.

Factors that affect the support of husbands for the participation of wives in the family planning program, these factors are: predisposing factors consisting of knowledge, attitudes, beliefs, value of children and desire to have it, age, education level, the number of children, employment, income, socio-culture to family planning, then the second is enabling factors consisting of development program, availability of family planning, access to family planning services, and the third is reinforcing factors consisting of the role of community leaders and the role of health workers (BKKBN, 2008).

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research known that Health Promotion At Puskesmas City South Area of City of Kediri known that most of respondent in good category is as much as 30 (58%) of respondents. Based on the results of the research note that Support Husband In Puskesmas City Southern Region of Kediri City note that most respondents in the category Enough is as much as 27 (52%) respondents. Based on the results of the research, it is known that the Attitude of Elderly Age Couple (PUS) in Following Family Planning Program at Puskesmas City of South City of Kediri City is known that almost half of the respondents in the category are 22 (42%) respondents. The result of data analysis shows that the value of $P = 0,005 < \alpha = 0,05$ thus There is Relation Role of Health Promotion And Support Of Husband With Patient Age Generation Attitude (PUS) In Following Family Planning Program In Puskesmas City Of Southern Region Of Kediri City.

REFERENCES

- A.Aziz, Alimul Hidayat. 2010. *Metode Penelitian Keperawatan Dan Teknik Analisis Data*. Jakarta : Penerbit. Salemba Medika.
- Anastasia marsila. 2013. *Faktor faktor yang mempengaruhi minat ibu memilih alat kontrasepsi*. Medan: Pasir pengaraian.
- Badan Kependudukan dan Keluarga Berencana Nasional 2012. *Arah Kebijakan dan Strategi BKKBN Tahun 2013*. Jawa Tengah.
- BKKBN. 2014. *Evaluasi Pelaksanaan Program KB Nasional BKKBN Provinsi Jawa Tengah*.
- Darwis, S. D. 2010. *Metode Penelitian*. Jakarta : EGC.
- DepKes RI. 2014. *Profil Kesehatan Indonesia 2014* : Menuju Indonesia Sehat 2015. Jakarta : Departemen Kesehatan RI.
- Handayani, Sri. 2010. *Buku Ajar Pelayanan Keluarga Berencana*. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Rihama.
- Hartanto Hanafi, 2010. *Keluarga Berencana Dan Kontrasepsi*, EGC, Jakarta.
- Junaidi, Wawan. 2009. *Pengertian-minat*. <http://mathedu-unila.blogspot.com>. (diakses 6 februari 2011).
- Kemenkes RI, 2010, *KB Pada Pasangan Usia Subur*, www.depkes.go.id.
- Muhajir, A. 2007. *Dukungan Sosial Keluarga*. Diambil dari <http://edukasi.com>. 2013.
- Notoatmodjo, Soekidjo. 2007. *Pendidikan dan Perilaku Kesehatan*. Jakarta : Rineka Cipta.
- Notoatmodjo, Soekidjo. 2010. *Metodologi Penelitian Kesehatan*. Jakarta : Rineka Cipta.
- Nursalam, 2008. *Konsep dan Penerapan Metodologi Penelitian Ilmu Keperawatan*. Jakarta : Salemba Medika.
- Saifuddin, Abdul Bari. 2010. *Buku Panduan Praktis Pelayanan Kontrasepsi*. Jakarta: Yayasan Bina Pustaka Sarwono Prawirohardjo.
- Setiadi, 2012. *Konsep dan Proses Keperawatan Keluarga*. Surabaya: Graha Ilmu..
- Sodik, M. A. 2014. Sikap Pencegahan Aborsi Ditinjau Dari Pengetahuan Tentang Bahaya Dan Resiko Kesehatan. *Strada Jurnal Kesehatan* <http://publikasi.stikesstrada.ac.id/wp-content/uploads/2015/02/9-SIKAP-SIKAP-PENCEGAHAN-ABORSI.pdf>
- Sodik, M.A., 2015. The “Kimcil” Phenomenon: Sexual Knowledge and Safe Sex Behaviour among

Adolescents in Kediri. *THE PROCEEDING OF INTERNATIONAL JOINT CONFERENCE CHALLENGES IMPLEMENTATION OF THE ASEAN ECONOMIC COMMUNITY (AEC) IN THE HEALTH SECTOR IN INDONESIA.*

Yogyakarta: Literasi Media Publishing.
https://www.academia.edu/31455750/Dasar_Metodologi_Penelitian

Siyoto, S. & Sodik, M.A. 2015. *Dasar Metodologi Penelitian.*

Sulistiyawati, 2013. *Pelayanan Keluarga Berencana.* Jakarta : Salemba Medika.

Sugiyono, 2011. *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif Kualitatif Dan R&D (Edisi Revisi).* Bandung : CV. Alfabeta.

Suryono, B. A. 2008. *Partisipasi Pria dalam Kesehatan Reproduksi.* Diambil dari <http://prov.bkkbn.go.id>.

WHO, 2014. *Health Promotion Glossary,* Geneva: WHO.2014.